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A new conceptual framework for assessing corporate financial performance. A sustainable approach

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Dates of submission: 24.08.2024

Date of publication: 28.12.2024

Abstract: *This study sets out to establish a new definition for the concept of corporate financial performance, mostly associated with the concept of corporate economic growth, highlighting the prevalence of the types of capital such as those specific to natural, human and social. These types of capital comprise resources such as: renewable and non-renewable natural resources (forests, oil deposits), the individual's health, well-being and knowledge, respectively social relationships based on mutual trust. The method of definition used comprises the sufficiency predicates and implies the development and transformation of four such predicates. Lastly, mathematic relationships are proposed in order to better evaluate the company's conceptual corporate financial performance, with regard to its consumption of resources specific to those of natural, human and social capital. Nevertheless, the mathematic models imply the existence of some so-called artificial realities, which represent conditions that are not fully reflected in the actual socioeconomic environment.*

Keywords: *Corporate Financial Performance, Sustainable Approach, Sufficiency Predicates, Mathematic Model*

1. Introduction

Corporate financial performance is a subject that is of paramount importance to researchers, corporate managerial and executive boards, investors, governments and various stakeholders alike (Kaya A., et al., 2024). The concept is mostly associated with the company's ability to survive and thrive within the socioeconomic environment, an environment that is characterized by competition, legal and ethical regulations and rapid shifts within the technological field (Abdel Basset M., et al., 2020). To this end, various theories elaborate methods and strategies by which the company, through its decisional stakeholders, can achieve the objective of being financially performant (Lam W.S., et al., 2021).

The process of corporate financial performance has as an output the creation of economic goods and services, which by reaching the end consumer generate economic welfare, improved quality of life and development. However, an issue that has been and is still being addressed by scholars, researchers, governments and international organizations is for how long can the actual characteristics of generating corporate financial performance be sustained. In other words, when will the inputs used by companies in achieving their financial performance be depleted? In light of the inputs mentioned, those specific to natural capital are of utter importance, as these are the basis of our socioeconomic development, followed by those specific to social and human capital. The latter of the three are responsible to some extent for enabling and enhancing innovative capabilities which in turn are a necessity for shifting the current state of affairs regarding socioeconomic development, both at micro and at macro levels.

On one hand, with respect to resource-based theory, corporate financial performance refers to the corporate's capabilities of achieving its targeted financial objectives through the efficient allocation and

use of the resources owned (Melynda S.T.A., et al., 2022). On the other hand, considering agency theory, corporate financial performance is determined by the degree by which the managers and the owners of the company can align their objectives so that agency costs that would result from the latter's divergences are minimized (Khan M.J., et al., 2024). Furthermore, in line with the stakeholder theory and with the legitimacy theory, corporate financial performance represents the company's effectiveness in considering various stakeholders as objectives themselves, rather than means of achieving financial goals. Such strategies of including various stakeholders in decision making places the company in a sphere where its solely financial performance is enlarged so that it comprises both environment and social performance (Sandberg H., et al., 2023).

If the previous theories refer to the strategies to be implemented by companies in order to achieve their financial performance objective, then concepts such as corporate social responsibility and the triple bottom line stand as the starting point for corporate financial sustainability. The latter are studied by researchers through the means of both Environmental, Social, Governance (ESG) indicators (Sandberg H., et al., 2023) and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) indicators (Qian C., et al., 2019). With considerations for both the above-mentioned definition of corporate financial performance and the necessity for sustainable practices in order for companies to achieve their financial objectives, this study sets out to establish a new definition for corporate financial performance. The definition is meant to be comprehensive from an efficient point of view.

The motivation behind this research idea is that, sharing the vision of renowned authors in the field of economics, such as Georgescu-Roegen and Daly, we believe that the existing approaches to both corporate financial performance and the possibilities through which it can be conducted indefinitely are lacking with regard to their theoretical and conceptual foundations. The reasoning behind this belief resides in the current rate of consumption of natural capital, which should gradually be replaced with substitutes such as potential new technologies resulted from the human capital's knowledge component and with social relationships based on mutual trust specific to social capital.

Corporate financial performance constitutes a subject that is addressed empirically rather than theoretically or conceptually. The reasoning behind this relates to the fact that it is easily accessible in numerical values through indicators such as return on assets, equity, investments, sales (Jyoti G. & Khanna A., 2021); the company's book value, market value; or compound indicators such as Tobin's Q ratio (Ionascu I., et al., 2022), the Kaplan and Zingales index (Bhattacharya S., & Sharma D., 2019), which measures the company's ability to contract external funding, or the Altman index and model (Marsenne M., et al., 2024), which predicts the chance of a company going into bankruptcy, thus highlighting its inability to survive in the socioeconomic environment. However, we do believe that this type of empirical approach does not entirely and comprehensively reflect the whole of corporate financial performance. In the following section we will highlight two series of aspects that will prove fundamental in the future for corporate financial performance. The first series refers to the inputs used, inputs that take values from a range of capitals, such as financial, human, intellectual, natural, physical and social capital. The second series refers to the 'side effects' of corporate financial performance which are called externalities. These, together with the first series of aspects constitute to some degree the focus of the previously mentioned ESG and CSR. However, the conceptual foundation of the externalities resulted in the aftermath of corporate financial performance is by far not incorporated into the empirically accessible ESG and CSR data and indicators, as these two are mostly calculated based on what the company says in its reports and policies, rather than actually being measured on the field (Ditlev-Simonsen C.D., 2022).

Therefore, within the following section we will elaborate a definition for corporate financial performance using the sufficiency predicates technique, while in the third section of the paper mathematical models will be presented in order to better understand the new conceptual approach proposed.

2. New conceptual approach to corporate financial performance

In order for future research to be better fitted for evaluating the companies' financial performance, we propose a model and a definition that places equal emphasis not only on the output, which is the corporate financial performance, but also on the capitals that constitute inputs for the process and on

the externalities resulted in the process's aftermath. Such a conceptual framework constitutes an efficient based approach that is developed in order to extend the effective one that is vastly empirically addressed through the indicators mentioned in the previous paragraphs. To this end, with respect to the first series of aspects mentioned earlier, corporate financial performance is achieved through the company's strategies and methods of using the resources at its disposal. These resources refer to types of capital such as human, natural, physical, technological, social and financial. The main emphasis on the sustainability of corporate financial performance resides within the implications of natural, social and human capital, as these represent a conglomerated resource pool with minimal negative external impact toward the socioeconomic environment. As a consequence of their minimised negative impact for procurement, as opposed to that of obtaining, for example, physical capital, their extensive used within the process of achieving corporate financial performance will therefore lead to minimised externalities, such as greenhouse gas emissions, accentuated income inequality and welfare.

The tool used in elaborating the definition objective of this paper is represented by the sufficiency predicate technique. This technique is used in the field of logics, philosophy and mathematics. It implies the creation of a number of sufficiency predicates that represent the necessary and sufficient conditions for a subject to be granted the conceptual characteristic of being corporate financial performance. The sufficiency predicates thus elaborated must in their turn respect three conditions. The first among the three is titled independency and requires that no sufficiency predicate is the logical result of another. The second condition is consistency which states that no sufficiency predicate is the opposite of another. Lastly, the condition of completeness according to which the intersection of the sufficiency predicates results in a set that is different from the empty set, from mathematics.

As such, we note $suff_{pred_i}$ as being the sufficiency predicate of type i where i takes values from 1 to n , $i = \overline{1, n}$. The independency condition is represented by the following relationship:

$$suff_{pred_i} \not\Rightarrow suff_{pred_j} \text{ and } suff_{pred_j} \not\Rightarrow suff_{pred_i}, \text{ for } i = \overline{1, n}, j = \overline{i + 1, n} \quad (1)$$

The consistency condition is highlighted by the following relationship:

$$suff_{pred_i} \neq (-1) * suff_{pred_j}, \text{ for } i = \overline{1, n}, j = \overline{i + 1, n} \quad (2)$$

Lastly, the completeness condition is underlined by the following relationship:

$$suff_{pred_1} \cap \dots \cap suff_{pred_i} \cap \dots \cap suff_{pred_n} = S \neq \emptyset \quad (3)$$

Having the logical conditions that must be met, we proceed to the construction of the sufficiency predicates that will grant a studied subject the conceptual characteristic of being corporate financial performance. Thus, in order to capture the concept of corporate financial performance in its whole complexity and interconnectedness with other factors, we propose the following sufficiency predicates:

$suff_{pred_1}$: it is the process undertaken by an entity;

$suff_{pred_2}$: it is conducted and regulated within a socioeconomic environment;

$suff_{pred_3}$: it implies the transformation of the owned capital;

$suff_{pred_4}$: it is reported with respect to the capitals consumed and to the externalities created.

The number of cases that must be analysed for the condition mentioned is equal to C_4^2 which is equal to $\frac{4!}{2!(4-2)!} = 6$.

The independency analysis implies the analysis of six possible cases. None of the four sufficiency predicates identified is the logical result of another. Thus, we respect the condition highlighted in relationship (1) for all of the four sufficiency predicates. Likewise, the consistency condition is validated, as not one of the four sufficiency predicates is the opposite of any other, as underlined in relationship (2). Lastly, we observe the simultaneous relevance of the four sufficiency predicates and affirm the fact that their intersection is different from the empty set.

Thus, we have the set $S_{CorpFinPerf}$ which comprises the four identified sufficiency predicates. As such, we define corporate financial performance as the process undertaken by an entity within a regulated socioeconomic environment that implies the transformation of its capital and is reported with respect to the capitals consumed and the externalities created.

$$S_{CorpFinPerf} = \{suff_{pred_1}, suff_{pred_2}, suff_{pred_3}, suff_{pred_4}\} \quad (4)$$

According to the proposed definition, we observe that the company's ability to survive and thrive is no longer strictly dependent on its ability to generate profit, according to a pure financial approach, but it is rather dependent on aspects specific to the triple bottom line and to corporate social responsibility as well. Therefore, the empiricism of corporate financial performance with respect to this type of approach might refer to measurements such as return on natural capital consumption (Zheng L. et Al., 2022), return on social capital created (True-Funk A. & Poleacovschi C., 2020) or profit after natural capital depletion.

3. Mathematical relationships

Within this section we will provide a series of mathematical measurements for the proposed definition of corporate financial performance, with respect to the inputs used and the externalities resulted in the aftermath of achieving the output.

First, with respect to the natural capital, as it is also highlighted within the environmental bottom line and within the corporate social responsibilities toward the environment, we propose the following mathematical relationship:

$$Corp_{FinPerfNatCap} = \frac{\Delta_{Sales}}{EcoFootprint} \quad (5)$$

Where Δ_{Sales} is a basic indicator which reflects the company's growth in sales and is used in determining the empirically studied return on assets and equity. With regard to the ecological footprint, *EcoFootprint*, it refers to the ability of the economic actor to fit its socioeconomic processes within the Erath's biological carrying capacities (Liao H., et al., 2024). The concepts of ecological footprint and carrying capacity have been studied by economists and ecologists alike among which we mention Daly, Costanza and Rees.

With regard to the measurement of the global ecological footprint and its repartition per economic agent we propose the commonly and empirically used volume of carbon dioxide emissions, as the former is difficult to be wholly estimated given the complexity of the natural ecosystems, their renewability rates and their interconnectedness among themselves and through the evolution of time. Thus, the mathematic relationship (5) changes to a more easily approachable one from an empirical point of view:

$$Corp_{FinPerfNatCap} = \frac{\Delta_{Sales}}{CO_2} \quad (6)$$

Where CO_2 stands for carbon dioxide emissions, therefore we will be measuring corporate financial performance by using return on carbon emissions, thus underling both the importance of financial results and that of a sustainable approach to the corporates' ability to survive and thrive. With regard to this approach, in order to mitigate the endogeneity issue related to the omission of a variable such as the corporate's activity sector, we propose a holistic approach as to encompass within the company's CO_2 emissions all of the three scopes related to greenhouse gas emissions. The inclusion of the three scopes will result in a CO_2 indicator that reflects the emissions from the company's direct and indirect activities such as supply chain acquisitions and electric energy purchase. With regard to the definition we proposed, carbon emissions consists both an externality, one we can consider that results in the aftermath of, for example, coal burning, and a consumption of natural capital, in the sense that a part of our planet's storing capacity is thus used.

Although the formula depicted in the mathematical relationship (6) is more accessible to empirical studies, the one shown in (5) offers a more comprehensive approach to the subject of sustainable finance as seen through the triple bottom line and corporate social responsibility. The reason behind this statement resides in the fact that the achievement of corporate financial performance uses an array of

natural resources much larger than solely the amount of greenhouse gas emissions. However, complex research is needed in order to make other measures of natural capital, such as water consumption and contamination or soil degradation, accessible to empirical studies (Zheng L. et Al., 2022).

Thus far we have highlighted the ‘natural efficiency’ behind corporate financial performance which is in line with its responsibilities toward the natural environment and the environmental bottom line. We extend our mathematic models so that we provide the promised holistic approach and proceed to develop models related to responsibilities toward society and in accordance with the social bottom line. For this we propose the mathematic relationship (7).

$$Corp_{FinPerf_{SocCap}} = \Delta_{Sales} * (SocValAdded - 1) \quad (7)$$

Where Δ_{Sales} has the same meaning as in relationship (5) and *SocValAdded* refers to the social value added generated by the company. This can refer to philanthropic activities, stakeholder engagement and value added, the balance between stockholder dividend payout ratio and the company’s capacity to reinvest its profits, employees’ salaries and time spent working. We can notice that the second factor consists of a difference by which we want to underline the fact that financial profit already has social implications as it tends to satisfy someone’s economic needs. In this case, that someone refers to the stakeholders in direct contact with the company, those being investors, employees and managers. What we do want to underline as an addition to corporate financial performance is its potential to generate social added value. As such, the new variable included, *SocValAdded*, can be measured as either a compound indicator or as a sole one. To this end, we offer a series of examples: percentage of net profit offered as philanthropic giving, the ratio between employees’ minimum wage and the country of residence regulation in this matter, expenditure with employees’ training. Social capital represents a means by which the company can preserve its financial performance through periods characterised by external shocks, such as the 2008 financial crisis (Lins K., et al., 2017). However, yet again, we believe that measurements based solely on the existence of certain social policies within the firm and its image within the media are not proper measurements for its social capital, as the latter is based, from a comprehensive point of view, on trust (Ditlev-Simonsen C.D., 2022; Sandberg H., et al., 2023).

The academically trained eye can observe that the mathematic relationships proposed by us require a specific ‘conceptual environment’ in order to be accessible to the empirical analysis. Such an environment is created through the means of a number of so called ‘artificial realities’. As such, for the side of corporate financial performance that is dependent on natural capital, we introduce a first artificial reality that states that the ecological footprint, the ecosystems’ renewable capacities and the Earth’s carrying capacity are rather objectively stated than subjectively. The second one would refer to the fact that all current individuals inhabiting the Earth are undoubtedly entitled to an equal share of the previously mentioned natural resources and services. With regard to the social capital characteristic of corporate financial performance, we introduce a third artificial reality which states the fact that all individuals represent an objective of equal importance to corporates’ planning, regardless of the type of impact the latter has on the former. The fourth and last artificial reality represents a conceptual intersection of social and human capital. It refers to employees’ salaries and to the fact that the salary integrally comprises the employee’s motivation, health, time spent working, productivity, education and skills.

By fusing together relationships (5) and (7) we obtain a sustainable approach to corporate financial performance, in the sense that we measure the social economic value created by the company through its consumption of natural capital.

$$Corp_{FinPerf_{EntroSustain}} = \frac{\Delta_{Sales}}{EcoFootprint} * (SocValAdded - 1) \quad (8)$$

At first glance we observe that relationship (8) underlines a synoptic view of corporate financial performance and conceptually highlights the importance of the resources specific to the capitals mentioned toward the achievement and maintenance of this corporate objective. The potential damage the company’s activities can have on the environment is directly influencing the ‘value’ of its financial profit, which in turn is subject to the company’s impact on the society.

4. Conclusions

The present paper achieves its objective of elaborating a comprehensive approach to corporate financial performance based on sustainable aspects. The definition thus proposed can serve various third parties such as scholars, corporate executives, policy makers in measuring financial objectives with respect to the natural resources consumed and to the social value added created. Furthermore, it provides a solid basis for future research in tackling either corporate financial performance or corporate sustainable finance through the lens of the resources embodied by human, natural and social capital. This type of approach will vastly enlarge the current state of the art with regard to corporate financial performance through empirical analysis of a new conceptual approach.

Natural capital, human capital and social capital have their prevalence in achieving corporate financial performance underlined by the fact that they constitute an input not only to the actual process of achieving corporate financial performance but also have constituted an input for the creation of the physical and financial capital used by the company in its current economic process. As such, although technology rapidly changes and is subject to substitutions and financial capital loses part of its value due to inflation, natural resources and services, the individuals' health and skills, and social relationship still represent inputs that cannot be substituted both from the economic process and from creating other forms of capital.

Although our approach targets corporate financial performance, we state that the mathematic relationships can be adapted to economic growth, thus creating a transition from microeconomic to macroeconomics. A macroeconomic approach benefits of more easily accessible indicators for empirical analyses. Such indicators might refer to gross domestic product growth, income discrepancies as reflected by the GINI index, natural rents, total volume of CO₂ emissions.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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